

Analysis of light cylinder and structure deformations of binary pulsars using TESS data

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Abstract

The pulsar binaries involve a variety of companion stars. The behaviour of each neutron star is specific around the distinguishable class of companion stars. Using the obtainable past data we compare it to the TESS data for the following neutron stars: PSR J1023+0038, XSS J12270-4859, to find the parameters which are time dependent(epoch is more than one decade). The parameters involved are the pulsar period, flux and the parallax angle;from these we can derive the parameters like the first derivative of period which is useful for determining the rate of change in kinetic energy when spin up or spin down. We also obtain the magnetic flux density as well as inertia through which we can determine the radius of the light cylinder.Considering that the magnetic dipole is perpendicular to the rotational axis we infer the dipole field which is proportional to p and derivative of p . In different stages of the pulsar they attain distortion in their structure based on their companion star. The accretion and glitches reform the structure of the pulsars from different stages like oblique spheroid to prolate spheroid. Inertia of the pulsar plays a major role in the variation of the structure of the pulsar. Studying the optically observed shape from the flux and dispersion measurement we can analyse the present shape of the pulsar with respect to the data.

Introduction

In September 1967, the first spinning neutron star was discovered by Jocelyn Bell which was initially mistaken as transmission from intelligent species (Little Green Men), which later opened a window to a new type of star- a supergiant collapsed core star of 10-25 solar masses with radius in order 10km. The stellar interior of a neutron star acts as a good conductor which is ionised. Charged particles are constrained to move along the magnetic field lines producing high energy pions and kaons. When star collapses from million km to a few km radius, Angular momentum is conserved by increasing the rotational rate by a factor proportional to rate at which star collapses.

Figure 1:magnetic dipole model of a pulsar,Figure credit: Lorimer and Kramer.

Light curve of binary pulsar 'PSR J1023+0038'

Figure 2:Time series data from all registered achieve.

Structure deformation

Neutron star can increase the spin called spin-up due to a few conditions such as absorbing the orbital matter from companion stars in the binary system reshaping the structure of neutron star into oblate spheroid; Due to Starquake which is similar to earthquake resulting in sudden increase in spin(called as glitches). Neutron star also has a spin down phase over its lifetime or due to an anti-glitch phenomenon where the shape of the neutron star becomes more spherical .Let's consider deformed neutron as a ellipsoid with semi major axis x, y, z as soon in figure: When $a=b=c$, the neutron star shape will be in Sphere. When $a \neq b \neq c$ (All three semi axes are not equal), the shape of the neutron star is ellipsoid. When any two axes are equal, the most possible shape of a neutron star is prolate and oblate. Oblate shape neutron star $a=b$

$$(x^2 + y^2)/a^2 + (z^2/c^2) = 1$$

Figure 3:Left: $a > c$, Oblate shaped neutron star; right: $a < c$, prolate shaped neutron star.

Light cylinder of pulsar

Neutron star acts an uni-polar generator as it is spinning magnetic dipole generating the radio pulses The total Lorentz force acting on a charged particle is

$$F = q(E + (V * B/C))$$

Charges in the magnetic equatorial region are responsible for building electrostatic fields which can cancel the magnetic force. The fields which are emerging from polar caps cross the light cylinder. It is an imaginary cylinder centered on the pulsar and aligned with the rotation axis at whose radius the co rotating speed equals the speed of light, so these field lines cannot close. Light cylinder radius:

$$R_{lc} = C * p/2 * \pi$$

P is the pulsating period of pulsar. The magnetic flux density at light cylinder radius is given as

$$B_{lc} = B_s * ((R_n/R_{lc})^3)$$

$$B_s = 3.2e + 19 * (P * P1)^{0.5}$$

$$P1 = P_2 - P_2/T_2 - T_1$$

$P1$ is first period derivative of pulsar, B_s is surface dipole, R_n is $10 * 6$ cm magnetic flux density

Analysis of light curve

The Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) succeeded Kepler in 2018. The data it collects are very similar to those from Kepler and K2, After collecting data from all observed achieves, removing the background and instrumental noise to improve signal to noise ratio. looking for transit and extracting the period of pulsar from each observation.

Figure 4:Improved signal too noise ratio of pulsar 'PSR J1023+0038'

Results

Parameters	Value
[1]Pulsating period	240 sec
[2]First period derivative	2602.392*e-8 sec
[3]Surface magnetic flux	2.52e+18 G
[4]Light cylinder Radius	1.145*e+10 m
[5]Magnetic flux at R_{lc}	1678742.482 G
[6]Deformed shape	Oblate Spheroid

Table 1:calculated parameters of binary pulsar 'PSR J1023+0038' from Tess, K2, Kepler data

Conclusion

In the process of analysing the light cylinder of the pulsars and shape deformation, we have calculated parameters like pulsar period, first derivative of pulsar, light cylinder radius, surface magnetic flux, magnetic flux at light cylinder radius and deformed shape according to 2021 of binary pulsar 'PSR J1023+0038'. Other pulsars 'XSS J12270-4859' still research is going on. Studying the light cylinder and structure deformation allows us to understand properties of Neutron star.

References

- The Australia Telescope National Facility Pulsar Catalogue
- Comparative Study of Pulsars Based On Emission Mechanisms
- Essential Radio Astronomy